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**The platform for sharing, initiating and
learning citizen science in Europe**

D2.2: Engagement and community- building plan

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Definitions and acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DG-Env	European Commission Directorate-General for Environment
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association /Verein der Europäischen Bürgerwissenschaften
F2F	Face-to-Face
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
LULC	land-use and land-cover change
PPSR	Public Participation in Scientific Research
the Platform	The EU-Citizen.Science platform
the Project	The EU-Citizen.Science project
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
Stakeholders	Those who have a stake or interest in the success of the Platform and the outcomes of the Project
Target Audience	Those groups who we wish to actively seek out to use the Platform, and engage with in the community of Users
Users	Those who will use the Platform
QH	The Quadruple Helix model
WP2	Work Package Two: Platform, Community and Network Building

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Executive summary

The *EU-Citizen.Science Engagement and Community-building Plan* is Deliverable 2.2 (D2.2) from the coordination and support action (CSA) EU-Citizen.Science, grant agreement (GA) 824580. It outlines how the project will ensure that target stakeholders engage actively and sustainably with the EU-Citizen.Science platform, both during the project period (2019-21) and beyond. It provides an overview of key target audience identified, and their prioritization, a deep understanding of needs and expectations of the target audience which has been selected as a starting point for the community engagement process, as well as suggestions for a series of actions that the project will implement to meet those expectations and therefore stimulate community engagement.

The main objectives of this deliverable are to:

- Explain the process leading to the identification of a key target audience group;
- Outline how the understanding of their needs and expectations has been achieved, through a research approach based on semi-structured interviews;
- Suggest concrete actions to address those needs and expectations, as well as keep this key community engaged in the preparatory phase and launch of the Platform;
- Plan future steps, in view of making the engagement and community-building plan an iterative process that starts with the publication of this deliverable, and evolves throughout the project, focusing on understanding and engaging all key target audience identified.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The EU-Citizen.Science project

Citizen science (CS) actively involves the public in scientific research that generates new knowledge or understanding, and thus has the potential to bring together science, society and policy makers in an impactful way. As a core dimension of Open Science, it opens up the opportunity for all members of society to take an active role in research, innovation and the development of evidence-based policy, at local, national and EU levels.

It is the ambition of the EU-Citizen.Science project ('the Project') to build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific enquiry, by developing a sustainable platform to act as a mutual learning space for citizen science, focusing on Europe, but relevant globally. The overall vision for the EU-Citizen.Science platform ('the Platform') is to aid the mainstreaming of citizen science in Europe, such that it becomes an appreciated and widely established means for the democratisation of science in Europe, as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: The vision, mission and objectives of the EU-Citizen.Science project

The building of the Platform is being pursued through three interconnected lines of activity:

1. Coordinating citizen science actions, and making use of existing resources in the presently fragmented citizen science landscape in Europe,
2. Engaging quadruple helix stakeholders at local, national and European levels, and
3. Creating a mutual learning space and a set of comprehensive, co-designed training modules for different target audience.

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In keeping with our mission, we aim to engage equally with citizen science participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society throughout the course of the project. In order to do so effectively, it is therefore necessary to have a clear understanding of who our target audience is, their needs and requirements, and how we can build a community of engaged users of the Platform.

1.2 The Purpose of this Deliverable

The second work package within the Project (*WP2: Platform, Community and Network Building*) forms both the foundation and the heart of the Project, and is where the core work of co-designing and implementing the Platform is performed.

WP2 contains three crucial assessment phases - the second of which is to identify the key target audience of the EU.Citizen.Science platform and propose strategies to actively engage them in the Platform. This work takes place within Task 2.1 '*Mapping of stakeholders, key networks & platform-community members; multi-level engagement model for community and network building*', culminating in two deliverables: Deliverable 2.2 '*Multi-level platform Engagement & Community Building Plan*', which is this report, and Deliverable 2.1 '*Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report*', which is submitted in parallel to this report.

This *Engagement and Community-building Plan* provides a detailed set of proposals for building a community that will use and populate the Platform. This report also forms the basis for the subsequent requirements-gathering activities that are contained within Task 2.2 '*Co-design of platform requirements (including end-user / community needs assessment and analysis of content formats*', which will culminate in Deliverable 2.3 '*Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report*'.

Engagement and community-building activities will ultimately be a key element in achieving the Project's core mission, which is to bring together individuals interested (or potentially interested) in citizen science, while providing an overall common understanding of the field. In the future, EU-Citizen.Science will be the central hub for citizen science in Europe, to:

- Promote and share the benefits of the Platform to reach as wide a community as possible from among our target audience,
- Raise awareness of citizen science more widely, so that more people are attracted to participate in projects across the globe - and also encouraged to launch their own projects, and
- Establish the foundations for a longer-term, sustainable community of practice that is actively engaged and responsive, leading to stronger, more integrated citizen science actions across Europe that are coordinated and strengthened through the platform.

This plan also builds upon the project's *Communication and Dissemination Plan* (D6.1), which sets out how the Project will share its outcomes and results, build a brand and raise awareness of the Project's concept and objectives.

2 Summary of D2.1 findings

As outlined in *D2.1, Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report*, the key stakeholders for EU-Citizen.Science are ‘Any person, group, or entity with a common interest or stake in the outcomes of the Project and the success of the Platform’.

Since its start, the Project has engaged with key actors who are implementing citizen science initiatives at the European level (either as project coordinators, project partners, third parties or project supporters), together with newcomers who can introduce and promote citizen science practices in their respective countries. The main stakeholder groups for EU-Citizen.Science can be summarized in six groupings, as shown in the image below. A detailed description of the composition of each stakeholder group is provided in D2.1.

Figure 4: The main Stakeholder groupings in EU-Citizen.Science

In order to more specifically focus on the actors who will be relevant for the success of the Platform, and how they will use it, we have also made a distinction between Stakeholders, Users and Target Audience. There is a great deal of overlap between those who have a stake in the success and impact of the Platform (the Stakeholders), those who will use the Platform (‘the Users’), and those groups who we wish to actively seek out and engage with, including those who are not yet involved in citizen science in any way and might not even be familiar with the term (‘Target Audiences’).

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A deeper understanding of the Platform's Users, and the expected use they will make of our Platform, will be presented in Deliverable 2.3 '*Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report*'. In this report we explore our Target Audience, and what would potentially motivate them to engage with the Platform in the near and far future.

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3 The EU-Citizen.Science Target Audience

The first step in the preparation of this engagement and community-building plan has been to reflect upon key Target Audience and how to address them. The groups in our Target Audience differ from the Stakeholder Groups defined in D2.1 because instead of being broad categories, they refer to concrete communities who wish to actively engage with the Platform, for a range of reasons. They also differ from the User Groups defined in D2.3, who may use the Platform in different ways, because here we focus our attention on common needs and motivations for all Users of the Platform.

EU-Citizen.Science is not a citizen science project, but a project to support citizen science across Europe. We therefore do not turn to the rich literature on participant engagement within CS projects, but instead focus on building a community of users and stakeholders of the Platform itself.

This forms the core element of our engagement and community-building plan, and it has led to the identification of a core community of practice which we believe should be engaged with first, during the development and launch phase of the Platform, in order to ensure that it is well designed and contains useful content. The success of our efforts to recruit users to the Platform who are completely new to CS will depend on them finding clear and useful materials there. We describe these two communities as our primary and secondary target audiences, not based on an order of importance, but rather on the timing of when to engage with them throughout the life of the project.

3.1 Primary Target Audience

The question that leads us to the identification of the primary EU-Citizen.Science target audience is:

Q. ‘Who will be the first community to use, and more crucially, populate the EU-Citizen.Science platform?’

Our answer is that the Consortium project partners, third-party partners, our immediate network of “Science of Citizen Science” professionals, and those undertaking similar initiatives to support citizen science in their home countries form the primary target audience. These groups will be critical to our aims of gathering and sharing good quality tools, guidelines and materials.

3.2 Secondary Target Audience

The groups in our Secondary Target Audience are those communities who will actively use the platform once it is up and running, and will take part in the community forums. This group consists of those identified within the User groupings:

- A broader community of “Science of Citizen Science” professionals.
- Citizen science Practitioners (scientists, DIY, CSOs and NGOs, educators)

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- Citizen science Consumers (science journalists, policymakers, funding bodies)
- Future potential citizen scientists (who are still not aware of citizen science).

With the support of the primary target audience, who can help to answer questions in the community forums, the secondary target audience will be more easily engaged, and encouraged to contribute their own tools, guidelines and materials as well. Successful engagement of the primary target audience is thus key to the successful engagement of the secondary target audiences.

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4. Needs and expectations of the EU-Citizen.Science primary target audience

In order to understand the needs and expectations of the primary target audience towards the future EU-Citizen.Science platform, we have selected a group of around 30 individuals to compose a gender balanced cluster, representative of the “Science of Citizen Science” professionals. Selected individuals share most of the following characteristics:

- Almost all of them work in academia, and in a few cases for international associations, funding agencies or other research bodies
- They may be personally involved in citizen science projects, but the main focus of their professional activities is to either foster, support or study the development of citizen science activities
- Their main community of practice is with peers engaged in similar activities (i.e. the support or study of CS)
- They have in most cases a long lasting experience in (the study of) citizen science
- They are either involved in the EU-Citizen.Science project, or in the COST Action CA15212, or in other national activities supporting citizen science.

Out of the 30 individuals we have reached out to, 24 were available for a semi-structured interview conducted by ECSA team members. Most of these interviews took place by phone, during the months of August and September 2019. Almost all EU-Citizen.Science partners and third parties have been interviewed as part of the sample. The same set of questions was asked to all participants:

Semi-structured interview questions

1. What are your expectations towards the EU-Citizen.Science platform, what would motivate you to use it, what would you like to find there (needs)?
2. Is there any particular inspiring resources that you would suggest?
3. What would you like to contribute to the platform, in terms of expertise or resources?

The first and last questions were aimed at collecting useful information for the preparation of this current Deliverable. Question number 2 provides insights which will be analyzed and presented within Task 3.2 of WP3.

Key needs and expectations

There are a number of common threads which have emerged in most of the discussions. We present here the most relevant ones:

1. Showcase (good) projects

One of the most shared elements between all interviewees is the expectation of finding inspiring citizen science projects on the Platform. The showcased projects should be searchable by various

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criteria, such as country, thematic interests, stakeholder categorization, silos, etc. It is interesting to notice that this expectation was not shared by all participants. According to some of them, EU-Citizen.Science doesn't need to list projects (as there are already other platforms dedicated to this). This view has been supported mostly by representatives based in countries that already have strong support for citizen science via national networks, national or regional funding, etc. Most of the participants from countries where citizen science is still struggling to get institutional recognition and a structured network advocate for EU-Citizen.Science to be a tool where it is possible to find "good, inspiring projects, in a clear and harmonious way."

One of the main questions which arises from the identification of this need, is how do participants define what they consider to be "good" and credible examples (of citizen science initiatives). This strongly links to selection criteria which are being identified in WP3. Most of the participants have underlined how the Platform should provide some kind of ranking, prioritization or identification of those which can be considered as exemplary projects to follow, get inspired from, replicate (for several aspects, such as volunteers engagement, data quality, societal impacts, etc.). Moreover, participants affirmed that such a tool would help them save time in searches for good quality resources that they often perform. The guarantee of knowing that what is on the EU-Citizen.science platform is by definition of good quality is perceived as one of the main added values by our primary target audience, as well as something that would motivate them to engage in the Platform.

2. Focus on impacts:

According to several participants, one of the main challenges they face in their daily work on citizen science, is the possibility to assess citizen science projects/initiatives/etc. by their impacts, rather than, more typically, by their field and target audiences involved. Participants value as highly important the possibility to get inspired by citizen science experiences by their impact, achievements, outcomes (such as for example policy impact, or community growth, or societal engagement, etc.). They acknowledge that this would be a particularly complex task to perform, but they also consider that this would be one of the most outstanding services that the EU-Citizen.Science could provide to the community, to support its growth.

3. A matchmaking service:

"Networking" and "Forum" are amongst the most commonly used words by participants when talking about key features of the Platform, as they expect it to support opportunities to network, collaborate, get in touch with peers, etc. Interaction seems to be one of the key needs of the primary community, as it has emerged in most of the interviews, under different wording:

- Catalogue of institutions, individuals
- Mentorship
- Meeting point
- Communication tool
- Networking
- Forum

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- CS contact points for EU countries
- Communities of interest

All these actions are already being performed by the members of the primary target audience, but mostly in an unstructured way. When asked to provide an example of the most valuable resource they use or often refer to in their work on citizen science, several participants answered that reaching out to colleagues for questions or suggestions was quite often more useful to them than any other resources such as websites, guidelines, etc. This clearly shows that there is a strong “Science of Citizen Science” community of practice, which could benefit from a Platform that supports their interactions, and mentors newcomers to citizen science.

4. Starter guidelines

Several respondents noted that the Platform needs to address the needs of citizen science beginners as well as experienced practitioners. “How to” start guides are considered as the most important resource that participants would like to find on the Platform, as well as basic information (e.g. a video explaining citizen science). A clear definition of citizen science has also been indicated as important and highly needed. Besides the strong need for “how to ...” guidelines, participants also mentioned other inspirational resources addressed at explaining how to set up a citizen science process, starting from what you want to achieve (therefore focusing on impacts, as mentioned in point 2). Other types of resources expected to be found on the Platform include:

- A map of citizen science projects
- A curated list of best resources (ranking)
- News and updates on CS
- Statistics at EU level for CS
- Best practices
- Guidelines
- Toolkits repository
- Calendar of events
- Stories
- "Living documents"
- Funding calls
- Apps

5. Support visibility

According to several participants, the Platform should give citizen scientists and citizen science projects more visibility, more voice. It could do so by for example publishing success stories of citizen scientists, or significant impacts achieved through citizen science. It should also foresee some forms of rewards for its contributors, and therefore supporters of citizen science.

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5 Action Plan

The Engagement Plan for EU-Citizen.Science will follow best practice in online community building, community engagement and community participation. We will draw on needs and expectations identified in the research process, as well as the deeper understanding of our Stakeholder groups achieved in D2.1.

5.1 Our Community Management Framework

Community management consists of 8 basic elements. Everything we do in building the EU-Citizen.Science community of Platform users must take these elements into account.

The key to getting really good at managing our community will be to develop a plan that spends the right amount of time on each activity throughout the Platform development. Most of the plan will be repetitive week after week, but always geared towards developing the community, not maintaining it.

1. **Strategy.** Establishing and executing the strategy for developing the community. Collecting data. Analyzing data. Establishing strategy. Developing an action plan. Communicating the strategy and action plan. Project managing.
2. **Growth.** Increase active membership of the community and convert newcomers into regulars. Direct marketing, promotion, referral/word-of-mouth. Optimize membership life-cycle funnel.
3. **Content.** Create, edit, facilitate, and solicit content for the community. Create content about the community. Use recognition and social influence principles.
4. **Moderation.** Remove obstacles to participation and encourage members to make contributions. Initiate discussions, develop and refine guidelines, solicit contributions, highlight popular topics, remove the bad stuff.
5. **Events and activities.** Create all opportunities to raise awareness of the EU-Citizen.Science platform at events being organised by project partners, and others in the wider CS community., Seek opportunities to recruit new members as well as keep active community members engaged.
6. **Relationship and influence.** Build relationships with key members and gain influence within the community. Recruit and manage volunteers. Build and manage an insider group.
7. **User experience.** Improve the community platform and participation experience for members. Increase social density, remove redundant features, add new elements, and refine the design.
8. **Project Integration.** Advocate internally within the consortium team and other partners to integrate project processes with community efforts. Measure and increase the ROI. Integrate the project design, structure, communication and distribution of Citizen Science know-how with the wider community of volunteers and scientists involved in Citizen Science.

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5.2 Starting small with Community Building

Although the EU-Citizen.Science Project will draw on existing communities of CS practitioners, such as the members of the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and the Citizen Science COST Action, we will essentially be building a new online community of Platform users. In order to do so effectively, our initial focus will be on:

1 Developing a core group of user community members. Develop a core small group of active platform users first. Spend time with each. Make the community of users part of something they're invested in. Be sure that by the time we launch the Platform to the wider public we have a dedicated group of people who are keen to participate.

2 Sustaining momentum. An online community with a low level of activity dies very quickly. We will need to plan out the first few weeks of our community so activity steadily increases. How are we going to either secure more of a platform user's time or recruit more platform users?

3 Appealing to a strong self-interest. Develop strong appeals to the self-interests of community members. Our members are more likely than usual to be interested in supporting the mission of the Platform to support and mainstream CS across Europe, and to be genuinely interested in the development of new tools, guidelines and material to address existing gaps, but we can't rely on that alone. We must also recognise that the users of our Platform will have career-oriented reputations as well, to be seen as leaders in the field, and valuable contributors to the state of the art of citizen science. We therefore need to ensure that active online community members are recognised for their talents/knowledge/skills amongst their peers.

4 Encouraging a sense of ownership. Take a co-creative approach to both the Platform design and the gathering of tools, guidelines and materials. Encourage our community members to feel a deeper stake in the success of the Platform through their own involvement in the early stages. Acknowledge key contributions to show the value added of those contributing actively, reward their input, but more importantly deepen their sense of ownership further.

5 Persuading our secondary target audience to make a second visit. Raising awareness amongst our secondary target audience groups will be fairly straightforward, and will lead to good initial traffic.. But that second visit is much harder. What are we going to ask a visitor to do in their first visit to ensure they return?

6 Concentrating activity. We will be following strict release planning for all new elements and functionalities on the Platform, to keep the activity concentrated in specific areas. This creates an active atmosphere, makes sure new sections are well-populated before they launch, and ensures unused features aren't indicating a quiet site.

5.3 Action Plan for engaging the EU-Citizen.Science primary target audience

In order to engage with the EU-Citizen.Science primary target audience, as well as fulfill their expectations, several measures will be taken, both in terms of Platform development and community-building. As noted above, it is very important that our primary target audience members feel ownership of the Platform through its (co-)creation process. Their engagement and satisfaction will lead to project partners and key stakeholders in the field becoming active users of the Platform, which is a key first step towards the mobilization of the rest of the citizen science community.

This will be achieved through:

- Regularly informing all identified primary target audience about platform developments
- Engaging project partners and third parties (as well as other institutions who might volunteer to join) in the next steps of gathering needs and expectations from secondary target audiences, by providing simple questions to perform in their local contexts (possibly in their local language) and report back to the WP2 leader
- Engaging project partners and third parties (as well as other institutions who might volunteer to join) in the identification of Users journeys, by providing ready to use workshop activities which they can easily run within their local context
- Regularly acknowledge their contribution to the process, as well as contributions emerging from their local communities
- Inviting primary target audience members to test the Platform before it is released
- Running iterative rounds of interviews, once the first version of the Platform is online, in order to understand whether it has successfully addressed their expectations and, if not, what it can do to ameliorate
- Support them with tutorials on how to use the platform, including concrete suggestions on how to register, use various functionalities, as well as how to use it to engage their local communities, and what is in there for them (i.e. services they need/expect).

During the interviews, each participant was asked what they would like to contribute to the Platform development, based on their personal and professional expertise. This has led to the collection of very valuable information on how key stakeholders could contribute to the process, stay engaged and feel ownership of the final outcome. A large variety of expertise has been identified, including:

- User journeys (Heuristic evaluation and Cognitive walkthrough)
- Testing the Platform with colleagues
- Producing video tutorials
- Reaching out to audiences completely unfamiliar with the concept of citizen science
- Understanding scientists' motivations to adopt citizen science
- Provide resources (templates and guidelines)

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- Translating citizen science projects into fields which are not biodiversity/environment, such as for example archeology, housing, elderly, etc.
- Addressing policy makers
- Addressing school teachers and students

Participants will be addressed at different stages of the Platform development process, and invited to contribute to it according to their identified expertise.

6 Next steps: the Engagement and Community Building plan as an iterative process

As identified in D2.1, the core User groups for the Platform can be divided into those who are ‘producers’ of citizen science, i.e. people who do citizen science, and those who are ‘consumers’ of citizen science, i.e. those who use the outcomes of citizen science. Both groups contain people who are acting in different contexts, and also reflect a range of experience levels from those who are new to citizen science (‘Interested’) to those who have active experience with citizen science (‘Active’).

6.1 The engagement of citizen science “Producers”

Citizen science “Producers” form the core of our Primary Target Audience, and will this be engaged during the design of the Platform using co-creational approaches, leading to the beta launch of the Platform in spring 2020. Upon beta launch, our engagement activities will broaden to include our Secondary Target Audience, who are also represented in the ‘Producers’ category, but with a larger representation of those who are new to the field. The image below shows Citizen science “Producers” categories, according to their level of involvement in citizen science (ranging from interested to active).

CS Practitioners, or “Producers”

Starting from October 2019, new sets of interviews will be done involving each time one of the key target audiences identified within the CS “Producers”. In particular:

- At least 10 interviews will be conducted with Scientists Practitioners

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- At least 10 interviews will be conducted with DIY / Citizen Practitioners
- At least 10 interviews will be conducted with CSOs / NGOs Practitioners
- At least 10 interviews will be conducted with Educator Practitioners

In a similar process as with the primary target audience, all interviews will be aimed at achieving a better understanding of each community's needs, expectations and expertise they would be willing to provide to the platform. Outcomes of the interviews will be collected in a shared document, and analysis of their outcomes will be provided in a [living document](#) where needs and expectations from each target audience will be identified. WP2 leader will regularly share updates on the ongoing research work with members of the primary target audience, as well as engage them in the identification of actions to engage members of the secondary audiences towards the Platform.

6.2 The engagement of citizen science “Consumers”

Citizen science “Consumers” will also get engaged in the Platform shortly after it's first beta version will be launched, although mostly likely not earlier than summer 2020. They will be invited to the Platform once tailored resources (i.e. training modules) are available for them. They will also be engaged through various project dissemination activities. The image below shows citizen science “Consumers” categories, according to their level of involvement in citizen science (ranging from interested to active).

Starting from January 2019, new sets of interviews will be done involving each time one of the key target audiences identified within the CS “Producers”. In particular:

- At least 10 interviews will be conducted with Decision Makers
- At least 10 interviews will be conducted with The Press / Media
- At least 10 interviews will be conducted with Policy Makers

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- At least 10 interviews will be conducted with Funding Bodies

In a similar process as with the primary target audience, all interviews will be aimed at achieving a better understanding of each community's needs, expectations and expertise they would be willing to provide to the platform. Also in this case, the outcomes of the interviews will be collected in a shared document, and analysis of their outcomes will be provided in a [living document](#) where needs and expectations from each target audience will be identified. WP2 leader will regularly share updates on the ongoing research work with members of the primary target audience, as well as engage them in the identification of actions to engage members of the secondary audiences towards the Platform.

6.2 Addressing the challenge of “mainstreaming citizen science”

In the Action Plan above we have outlined how to reach out to and engage with our two core Target Audience groups. The awareness-raising, communication and dissemination activities described in the Deliverable 6.1 ‘Communication & Dissemination Plan serve to support these activities further. The expanded reach of the Consortium Partner’s through their networks of contacts and influence allows us to reach a good proportion of both the active and potential citizen science practitioner communities.

However, we acknowledge that there are a number of challenges to mainstreaming citizen science, which is the ultimate mission of this Project. Throughout the course of the project we will also be seeking opportunities to address these head on, and will collaborate closely with our Primary Target Audience in order to do so.

During the joint COST / EU-Citizen.Science workshop held in Brussels in April 2019, participants identified and ranked the main challenges to mainstreaming citizen science. Several of those ranked among the top ten challenges emphasize the need for engagement in citizen science, and a dedicated space in which to do so:

- Find places/opportunities to explain citizen science to “people not used to science” (ranked 2 out of 18).
- A lot of people are already doing citizen science, but they don’t call it ‘citizen science’, so it is hard to find them and connect with them (3).
- To find a (structured) way to include different citizen science initiatives so that many practitioners and newcomers in the field realize that they are, to some extent, part of the same group (4).
- Increase the diversity of participants, reaching under-represented communities (7).
- (Local) governments, in general, don’t know/understand what citizen science is and are not aware that citizens can contribute to tackling societal challenges (9).
- Raise awareness of the fact that citizen science can be a powerful tool to improve quality of life/ communities/etc. → concrete impacts, not just one more fun activity (10).

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From this it is clear that the building of the EU-Citizen.Science Platform could play a key role in addressing these challenges. By treating the Engagement and Community Building Plan contained in this deliverable as a ‘living document’ that can constantly be added to and improved upon over the course of the project, we will catch as many of these opportunities as possible.

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ANNEX 1: List of semi-structured interviews participants

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